

DOES AWARENESS, TRAINING AND ADAPTING TO CYBER RISKS REDUCING COMPUTER FRAUD? EVIDENCE FROM JORDANIAN BANKING SECTOR

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Abstract:

This paper seeks to investigate the mediating effect of adapting to cyber risks on the relationship between awareness and training and reducing computer fraud, based on a literature review covering the works specializing in cyber risks and fraud. The scope of the study encompasses the Jordanian banking sector, and the internal auditors and IT auditors were identified as the respondents for the questionnaire survey. The findings reveal a significant effect of awareness and training in reducing computer fraud. Also, adapting to cyber risks mediates the relationship between awareness and training and reducing computer fraud. Therefore, it is very necessary to increase awareness and training for the employees of the banking sector in particular by having the appropriate software skills to avoid falling into the trap of cyber security violations that incur them. Aside from enriching the knowledge on cybersecurity risks and fraud in the banking sector, this study can stand to deliver large benefits to the cyber security community.

Keywords: cyber-security risks, awareness and training, computer fraud, protection motivation theory.

1. Introduction

The rapid growth witnessed by communications technology has contributed significantly to improving performance when providing services and shortening time and effort, which has accelerated the pace of completion of foreign economic solutions and investment (Napetvaridze & Chochia, 2019). The transactions and operations practiced by the global banking system in the past years varied, there is no doubt that advanced technology had a clear impact on these operations, as many of these operations are carried out digitally through special programs to achieve the banking system prospects (Gono, 2013; Usman & Shah, 2013). Nowadays, in many cases, the traditional bank theft is no longer a prevalent issue as in the past, and the reason for this is that bank money is not kept only in bank vaults (Bank for International Settlements, 2016). Banks have bypassed the issue of face theft due to the presence of their money in cyberspace through advanced technologies and data networks (Jolian & Suraya, 2014, Hamdan, 2013). This led the banks to alert the need to adapt to the requirements of the

stage and the modern trends of conducting electronic business, taking into consideration taking the necessary measures to protect these banks from electronic crimes and their potential risks (Jolian & Suraya, 2014; Bada et al., 2019).

According to (Central Bank of Jordan, July, 2021) information in banking system is the most valuable asset because it forms the cornerstone of any idea that adopted in the investment community. In the massive technological revolution, real cyber interfaces for cyber security in different financial sectors are very important tools in banking system.

The wide space could be used to transfer and provide banking services, and to control information related to banking data in which it would be exploited by electronic thieves who seek money and aim to obtain it in any way, especially those funds that are in banks vaults or through ATMs or through the transfer of money from one account to another in illegal ways which will negatively affect the banking system safety and society's economies. (Al-Alawi & Al-Bassam, 2020; Hamdan & Al-Hajri, 2021).

A cyber risk defined as the mixture of the likelihood of cyber events occurring and their effect (Aldasoro et al., 2020; Hamdan & Al-Hajri, 2021). A cyber event, in turn, is any noticed incidence in an information system in which it can be jeopardizes the cyber safety of an information system or the information the system progressions, supplies or transfers; or interrupts the sanctuary policies, sanctuary actions or satisfactory employ strategies, whether bring about from malevolent action or not. Cyber risk is one practice of operational risk (Aldasoro et al., 2020; Tsai & Chan, 2007; Hamdan & Al-olimat, 2021).

Fraud is defined as the purposed distortion of information or identity to cheat others, it can inflict significant damage on the organizations (Rantala, 2008; Dzomira, 2014). Seemingly, this explanation could be revised for computer fraud, by necessitating the employ of a computer or other electronic sources in the instruction of the deceitful performance. Generally, computer fraud should involve the alike elementary explanation of classical fraud, whereas using newfangled contestants that adjust its employ for electronic means.

Cyber security governance denotes to the module of initiative governance that reports the initiative's dependency on cyberspace in the existence of opponents (Harknett & Stever, 2009). Therefore, cyber security governance includes evidence schemes security governance; it known that it relies on to how closely or generally, the initiative interprets information security (Hamdan, 2017; Trautman, 2015). Conversely, even though features of information security governance might report information external of cyberspace, the information flow among the non-cyber and cyber fields is so predominant that in overall it is desirable for cyber security governance to include information security governance.

Organizations are increasingly concerned about fraud and threats to data confidentiality, integrity and availability, cyber risks and fraud are rapidly evolving. When data are compromised and critical infrastructure and services are impacted, the cost to organizations and damage to trust and reputation can be very large. Most organizations use pragmatic solutions to address cyber-attacks, but much uncertainty remains about whether such solutions

are able to address threats before they cause too much damage, whether investments for the protection of important assets are appropriate and optimal.

Specifically, the financial service sector such as banking has its own unique strains of fraud to worry about (Duffy 2003). Thus, more work is needed in this area and collaboration between governments, academia, and industry. In this manner, this study has focused on investigating the mediating effect of adapting cyber risks on the relationship between awareness, training and reducing computer fraud in the Jordanian banking sector, to avoid or reduce future cyber-security threats.

2. Literature review

There is a large literature that talk about cyber security threats. Many researchers interest in this area: (Carey & Manic, 2016; Tsai & Chan, 2007; Arulanandam et al., 2014); Brown & Liu, 2016; Kallus, 2014). One form of cyber-attack is that some actors insert themselves as a threat to the exchange of trusted data, between the parties involved in the banking system through malicious programs designed to disable IT devices or steal data. Customer data using scripting via specific sites used to find a vulnerability in the Internet, that allow attackers to penetrate the activities of victims with some weak applications, or theft the sensitive data in email messages, to install malicious programs within these messages that appear to be from a trusted source and thus obtain passwords stored in computers (Aldasoro, et al., 2021, Arulanandam et al., (2014).

2.1 Computer Fraud

Computer fraud is a subsection of computer crime; were computer fraud employs electronic means to display deceitful information as a present of fraud (Arulanandam et al., 2014; Cronan et al., 2006). The deceitful actions presently occurring that employ electronic means are mainly an expansion of classical prevailing fraud actions manipulating a newfangled medium (Romney et al., 2015; Usman & Shah, 2013).

Claessens et al. (2002) and Usman and Shah (2013) Found that fraud operations aim to access the bank accounts of bank customers in order to steal their money or transfer it to other bank accounts; this could be done by using bank credentials such as; personal identification numbers, passwords and others. Sometimes they steal small amounts and other they steal as much money as possible, and these thieves may aim to damage the reputation of the banks by blocking the banking servers of customers, so that they cannot access their bank accounts, and it may take various forms such as robbery at ATMs, money laundering or fraud on credit cards online (Hamdan, 2013; Jolian & Suraya, 2014).

Anderson and Poole (2001) they were interested in studying crime via the Internet through hacking enthusiasts, the problems they cause to banks and the police, and the extent to which the traditional law applied to these fraudsters, they suggest the possibility of improving ways of dealing with these fraudsters via the Internet by understanding the economic perspective of their fraud.

2.2 Awareness and Training

Staff training is very important in rising awareness between employees and inspiring them to take into consideration the cyber intimidations and countering steps, even if they are not portion of their mission. To protect the business from any bout, staff-training is very important in creating awareness between employees and motivating them to pay extra attention and care to cyber intimidations, with these being the best-known strategies employed in contradiction of future cyber intimidations (Al-Alawi, 2006; Bada et al., 2019; Al-Alawi & Al-Bassam, 2020).

Florêncio and Herley (2011) and Dzomira (2014), dealt with the issue of weaknesses in the banking sector from a defensive point of view, and this requires the urgent need for mechanisms that increase the degree of awareness and take strict measures to confront electronic crimes that occur in the banking system. It is clear here that studies related to this issue in the past did not live up to the hoped-for level to mitigate potential risks and combat this type of crime (Trautman, 2015).

Cyber-security awareness refers to the status of presence aware of accomplishment-protected errands on a computer (Bulgurcu et al., 2010; Jolian & Suraya, 2014), studies have intensive on diverse features of awareness. For example, some have studied consciousness of computer practice policies (e.g., Cronan et al., 2006), others have examined security countermeasures (e.g., D'Arcy et al., 2009) and so on. The multiple aspects collectively include comprehensive information about general guidelines of information security, basic education on security risks and consequences of cybersecurity intimidations, and chasing internet practice for typical actions (Choi et al., 2013; Dzomira, 2014). On the other hand, trainings agendas presented to teach employers on satisfactory harmless and secure practice of computers, and the hazards tangled in mistreating the computers.

2.3 Adaptation to Cybersecurity Risks

Adaptive security, is a method that has converted further commonly employed in reaction to a speedily varying the set of performs that syndicates software progress and information technology processes setting and interconnectedness of the whole things. The aim of adaptive security is to generate a response round of intimidation discernibility, revealing and deterrence that steadily converts further operative.

2.3.1 Cyber Security Policies

Cyber security policies are of great importance because the various forms of cyber- attack and data breaches are very costly. Developing national cyber possibility tactics and increase the alertness of users exercising, educational agendas and engross in international assistance, create a public-private corporation, organizing the collaboration among public activities and improve national cyber possibility tactics, (Napetvaridze & Chochia, 2019).

On the other hand, information security policy ropes suitable performance amongst staffs by providing that perfect tutoring of tasks to track relations and circumstances of such policies (Siponen et. al., 2014). Staffs who appropriately track information security policies are resources to structural security (Flowerday & Tuyikeze, 2016). It links the breach among the

prospects of an organization and how people donate to the appropriate application of information security policy, which should be very strong to recognize. Furthermore, those policies are generated for staffs, who should continuously be considered during the strategy development procedure (Yazdanmehr & Wang, 2016).

The Cyber Security Policy defines the rules of conduct for various activities such as; the encryption of email attachments and the limitations that imposed on the use of social media (Yazdanmehr & Wang, 2016). A cyber- catastrophe administration plan at a national level; is a very vital element in a national cybersecurity policy, as it emphasizes on the national harmonization and vindication exertions through the catastrophe. Many cyber-incidents happen on a daily base and alleviated punctually at a functioning level, deprived of unavoidably foremost to a catastrophe state. There are many mechanisms needed to clarify with regard to cyber crises, perhaps the most important of them are: appropriate coordination of the immediate response to the crisis, careful management of information, public affairs procedures related to the cyber- attack, trying to mitigate the severity of the crises, as much as possible, and other measures that can be taken to reveal the crisis for analysis and solution, and therefore, try to end it in an appropriate manner, in light of the direct response (Napetvaridze & Chochia, 2019, Guttman & Roback, 1995).

2.3.2 Cyber Risk Management and Assessment

Risk management associated to information security, defined as the practice of measuring uncertainty in order to taking ladders to diminish it into a satisfactory level, and preserving that level of uncertainty (Guttman & Roback, 1995). Consequently, administrations should start through evaluating the impendence and weak points related with their information schemes. The assessment of the information weak to impendence likewise requires to measure at this point of the manner. At this stage, a value-weakness connection that aids classify which information should accept the security possessions could industrialize (Yazdanmehr & Wang, 2016). This connection would classify information from high into low for together value and weak point (Hamdan & Al-Hajri, 2021). Next, administrations should diminish information security uncertainty to a satisfactory level. This assurance is an administration instrument for decreasing the uncertainty of financial losses related with Internet-Related Breaches, (Gordon et al., 2003, Dzomira, 2014).

In this case, there must be a trade-off between what the company can invest in the issue of protection from security violations and what it can pay as insurance against Internet risks. Accordingly, lower levels of security protection require higher levels of Internet risk insurance from a cost-benefit perspective, and vice versa. This cost-benefit trade-off can reduce the risk of security breaches and the purchase of insurance, which in turn will also affect the level of residual risk and thus, this call for organizations to invest in intrusion detection systems, so that they have contingency plans in place to rectify potential breaches (Gordon et al., 2003; Yazdanmehr & Wang, 2016).

Risk Assessment is an essential portion of information security management, and it allows organizations to classify weaknesses and intimidations, though also notifying the select of cost-

e-actives controls (safeguards & countermeasures) to discourse possible intimidations (Cherdantseva, et al., 2016). Ionita (2013) designates risk assessment as an organized or semi-structured tactic of scrutinizing the security of a system, classifying frail spots, and choosing satisfactory controls. In general, risk management is a procedure of managing uncertainty to a satisfactory level inside an organization and classically involves of two chief phases recognized as risk assessment and risk treatment (Bojanc & Jerman 2013; Yazdanmehr & Wang, 2016)

According to the (ISO/IEC, 27005:2011) standard, risk assessment contains of two procedures, risk analysis & risk evaluation. Risk assessment includes an incessant iterative procedure, which turns round classifying, scrutinizing, arranging, justifying and controlling security risks. In assessing the risk of an information technology system, numerous aspects taken into account, containing classifying the asset, intimidation, weakness and effect.

The goal of risk assessment is to recognize the present system and environment in order to classify risks through scrutiny of the data gathered, which aids administrations to make security conclusions reliable with their risk management mechanism, despite the level of risk intrinsic in the appraisal procedure (Ross, 2012). Risk assessments are aimed either to notify decision-makers and sustenance risk reactions, as part of a security audit, compliance initiative, or to sustenance security reasonable decisions (Ionita, 2013; Ross, 2012; Hamdan & Al-olimat, 2021).

2.3.3 Protection Controls

There are many strategies that used to make a protection controls in cyber security: display and evaluate the efficiency of controls, create internal and external information foundations for hazard intellect and susceptibility data, observing them frequently and taking suitable action for high-precedence objects (Ross, 2012). On the other hand, performing episodic risk valuation appraisal, analyzing and apprising the facility's intimidation model could implement to make controls (Lenaeus et al., 2015; Yazdanmehr & Wang, 2016).

2.3.4 Cyber Incident Detection

Numerous kinds of information security incident could be classified as a cyber-security incident, extending from thoughtful cyber security raids on serious nationwide substructure and main planned cybercrime (Arulanandam et al., 2014; Cronan et al., 2006), out of hacktivism and elementary malware raids, to inside misapply of structures and software break. Those are some examples: small –limit criminals, individuals or groups just for enjoying, replying to a challenge to achieve a financial prize or restricted disturbance or vengeance (Jason & Ian, 2013, Hamdan, 2017).

2.3.5 Cyber Incident Response and Recovery

According to Littlejohn and Shinder, (2002) and Munaiah, et al. (2019) ecommerce, on-line banking and related technologies have resulted in millions of dollars of financial transactions taking place across network connections, and as banks expand their array of online services to clients; the risk of Internet Computer Fraud (ICF) increases and the risk landscape changes. Financially motivated high-profile attacks have observed across the globe with the growing

patronage of e-banking services and its anticipated dominance in the near future. Some of the known factors that contribute to the acute problem of security must be addressed (Usman & Shah, 2013; Trautman, 2015). However, people cannot redefine fraud because it has been committed through cyberspace, and further mentions that, because most victims of cybercrime are high-profile bank customers, they were reluctant to announce or admit in public that they have successfully being defrauded by some cyber-criminal (Dzomira, 2014, Usman & Shah, 2013).

According to Gono (2013) and Dzomira (2014), fifteen banking institutions have already introduced mobile banking products in partnership with mobile operators and the number of banking institutions venturing into mobile banking are on the increase. The volume of mobile payment transactions and the volumes of internet transactions also increased substantially. However, according to (Trautman, 2015), as more businesses and customers launch their money into cyberspace, opportunities for 21st century tech-savvy thieves also increased.

2.3.6 Testing

According to Munaiah, et al. (2019) and Jolian and Suraya (2014) the bank tests the components of the information and communication technologies environment after the occurrence of a cyber-event and coordinates with the concerned parties through: execute penetration tests of critical systems in a timely manner, then periodic assessment of vulnerabilities and security gaps for critical systems, their supporting and supportive systems, in both internal and external networks (Ross, 2012, Gordon et al., 2003, Dzomira, 2014)). The next step is to carry out continuous and effective monitoring of the bank's systems to detect any defect in any of the components of the information and communication technology environment (Littlejohn & Shinder, 2002). Finally, developing a comprehensive testing program to verify the effectiveness of cybersecurity policy and programs (Bulgurcu et al., 2010; Jolian & Suraya, 2014).

3. Research model and hypotheses development

3.1 Research Model

The present study mainly aims to discover the effect of awareness and training in reducing computer fraud in the Jordanian banking sector. Also, the study investigate the mediating effect of cyber risks adaptation on the relationship between awareness and training and reducing computer fraud. Literature dedicated to the topic was reviewed and the findings showed studies on cyber risks and computer fraud involving developing countries generally neglected, leading to a literature gap in this topic.

Back and Guerette (2021) proposed the Inter-Loop Anti-Phishing Model (ILAPM) that draws on protection motivation theory, expanded prominence interpretation theory, and risk analysis. This proposed model illustrates the continuous interdependence of avoidance and adoption cognitive systems in anti-phishing behavior, and continuous interdependence of education, awareness, and training. Based on these theoretical frameworks, Back and Guerette (2021) and Hanus and Wu (2016) explained that individuals engage in threat appraisal and coping

appraisal and consequently induce protective behavior. In the same context, Li et al (2019) suggest that the awareness regarding threats is necessary for the employees to take preventive measures. In other words, awareness and training activities should positively impact assessing the credibility and success in deception and phishing detection; in addition, these training activities should enhance in-depth understanding of social engineering and phishing techniques so that online users succeed in detecting cyber threats and avoid falling for phishing schemes (Back & Guerette, 2021; Menard et al., 2017).

In line with the proposed model, the security awareness and training induces and encourages users to enforce protective actions against fraud. In view of that, the protection motivation theory are applied in the present study to discover the effect of awareness and training in reducing computer fraud in Jordanian banks. Relevantly, the study model can be used to clarify the connections among awareness and training, cyber risks adaptation, and computer fraud.

Fig. 1. The proposed model

3.2 Hypotheses Development

From the literature, these factors were found to impact on reducing computer fraud: awareness, training, and adapting to cyber risks. Based on the above, the following hypotheses are proposed;

H₁: There is a positive relationship between awareness and training and reducing computer fraud.

H₂: There is a positive relationship between awareness and training and adapting to cyber risks.

H3: There is a positive relationship between adapting to cyber risks and reducing computer fraud.

H4: Adapting to cyber risks mediates the relationship between awareness and training and reducing computer fraud.

4. Methodology

According to Blaikie and Priest (2019), the research design consists of the structure of the investigation and the strategy to use to determine the research questions answers and to resolve the issue at hand. A research design primarily represents a roadmap for researchers to determine the answers to distinct problems, and a master plan that specifies the methods and procedures to be adopted for data collection and analysis and it is essential for every study (Zikmund et al., 2013). It encapsulates sets of rational decision-making processes that serve the study purpose (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

Moreover, the objectives of the study, information availability and research cost all impact the choice of research design to be employed (Zikmund et al., 2013). Thus, this study relied on the descriptive approach and the inferential approach in conducting it in order to identify the impact of awareness and training in banks in reducing computer fraud by having adaptation to cyber risks as a mediating variable, and this approach is based on an accurate and detailed interpretation of the problem by defining its conditions, components and dimensions, describing the relationships between them, analyzing, measuring and interpreting data, and arriving at an accurate description of the phenomenon or problem in a holistic manner that is useful in generalizing the facts or knowledge that it was extracted and helps a reasonable amount of future prediction of the phenomenon (William et. al., 2012:413).

4.1 Population and Sample

Survey research was used in this study involving the use of a questionnaire with 5 points Likert scale for data gathering. The questionnaire was pretested with the help of a number of relevant experts and banks. A total of 24 banks operating in Jordan made up the study population, where the researcher published (Online Questionnaire) via (Google Drive), using the (Purposive Sample) method on internal auditors and IT auditors. Overall, 232 copies of the questionnaire were completed and valid for statistical analysis.

4.2 Measures

A substantial portion of the measurement items was referenced from prior research (e.g., Arulanandam et al., 2014; Cronan et al., 2006; Romney et al., 2015; Usman & Shah, 2013; Jolian & Suraya, 2014; Trautman, 2015; Florêncio & Herley, 2011; Al-Alawi, 2006; Bada et al., 2019; Al-Alawi & Al-Bassam, 2020; Rantala, 2008; Aldasoro et al.; 2020; Tsai & Chan, 2007; Hamdan & Al-olimat, 2021; Cherdantseva et al., 2016), with adjustments made as needed to the original items based on the research context in this study. With the exception of demographic factors, all of the measurement items were scored using a 5 point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

4.3 Reliability

The coefficient of (Cronbach's Alpha) was relied on to measure the stability of the internal consistency of the study items, the results of which are shown in Table (1).

Table 1: The value of the coefficient (Cronbach’s Alpha) to measure the stability of the study instrument

Variable type	Independent	Mediator						Dependent	Overall index	
Variables	Awareness and training	Cyber security policies	Cyber security risk management and assessment	Protection controls	Detecting cyber incidents	Responding to cyber incidents	Testing	Adapting to cyber risks	Computer fraud	
Cronbach’s Alpha	0.874	0.744	0.773	0.850	0.824	0.849	0.863	0.924	0.781	0.960
No. of items	12	7	5	6	4	4	4	30	5	47

It is clear from Table (1) that the value of the internal consistency coefficient (Cronbach’s Alpha) for the paragraphs of the study tool ranged between (74.4%-92.4%) and with a stability degree of (96%) for all paragraphs, and (Sekaran & Bougie, 2020: 325) indicated that the limit of the minimum stability coefficient (Cronbach’s Alpha) is (0.70), and the closer the value is to (1) one, i.e. 100%, this indicates higher degrees of stability for the study tool, and accordingly, all the internal consistency coefficients mentioned in the above table are a good indicator of the stability of the study tool and the possibility of rely on it in statistical analysis.

5. Results

The arithmetic averages, standard deviations, rank, relative weight and degree of approval were calculated in order to know the opinions of the sample members towards the study variables, and the degree of relative approval was determined according to the following equation:

$$\text{Category Length} = \frac{\text{Maximum Alternative} - \text{Minimum Alternative}}{\text{Number of Levels} - 1} = \frac{5 - 1}{3} = 1.33.$$

If the arithmetic mean falls between (1-2.33) it is considered within the low level, and if it ranges between (2.34-3.66) then it falls within the medium level, and if it exceeds (3.66) it is considered within the high level (Subedi, 2016). The results of the descriptive analysis of the study variables were as follows:

5.1 Descriptive Statistics for the Study Variables

Table (2) shows the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, relative weight, degree of agreement, and rank of the respondents' answers towards the study variables, and the results were as follows:

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of the study variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	Percentage%	Application	Ranking
Awareness and training	4.23	0.443	84.6	High	
Cyber security policies	4.25	0.407	85	High	1
Cyber security risk management and assessment	4.22	0.475	84.4	High	2
Protection controls	4.11	0.546	82.2	High	5
Detecting cyber incidents	4.14	0.589	82.8	High	4
Responding to cyber incidents	4.10	0.637	82	High	6
Testing	4.16	0.607	83.2	High	3
Adapting to cyber risks	4.17	0.435	83.4	High	
Computer fraud	4.19	0.522	83.8	High	

Table (2) shows that the independent variable (awareness and training) has achieved an arithmetic mean of (4.23) with a relative weight (84.6%), a high degree of approval, and a standard deviation (0.443), and we note that the dimension (cyber security policies) achieved the first rank among The dimensions of the mediating variable (adaptation to cyber risks) with a relative weight (85%) and a high degree of approval, and after (cybersecurity risk assessment) achieved the second rank with a relative weight (84.4%) and a high degree of approval.

As for the (tests) dimension, it came within the third rank with a relative weight (83.2%) and a high degree of approval, and in the fourth rank it achieved after (disclosure of cyber incidents) with a relative weight (82.8%) and a high degree of approval, and it achieved after (protection controls) the ranking The fifth, with a relative weight (82.2%) and a high degree of approval, and came after (cyber incidents response) in the sixth place, with a relative weight (82%) and a high degree of approval, as the arithmetic averages ranged between (4.10-4.25), and the general index of the median variable was (Adaptation to cyber risks) (4.17) with a high degree of approval, relative weight (83.4%) and standard deviation (0.435), and the arithmetic mean of the respondents' answers towards the dependent variable (computer fraud) was (4.19) with a relative weight (83.8%) and a high degree of approval. and with a standard deviation of (0.522). We note that the standard deviations of all dimensions are close, and this indicates the lack of dispersion in the answers of the study sample members in their answers towards the paragraphs of the study tool.

5.2 Hypotheses Test Results

5.2.1 The Result of the First Hypothesis Test:

H₁: There is a positive relationship between awareness and training and reducing computer fraud. This hypothesis has been subjected to (Simple Linear Regression) analysis and the results shown in Table (3) have been reached.

Table 3: Results of the simple linear regression model for the first hypothesis

Model Summary			ANOVA			Coefficient					
R	R ²	Adj R ²	F	F. Sig	DF	Description	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig
0.662	0.438	0.436	179.358	0.00	231	Awareness and training	0.780	0.058	0.622	13.392	0.00

Table (3) indicates the value of the correlation coefficient of (R=0.662), which indicates that there is a strong relationship between awareness, training and the reduction of computer fraud. Also, the value of (R=0.438) which indicates that (43.8%) of the variance was able to be explained by raising awareness and training in reducing computer fraud.

We note from the results of the table that there is a statistically significant effect of awareness and training in reducing computer fraud, which appears through the value of (T.Sig) equal to (0.00), which is less than (0.05) and also through the value of (T) calculated and equal to (13.392), which is greater than its tabulated value (1.96). Accordingly, we accept hypothesis H₁, where it was proven that there is a positive, statistically significant effect of awareness and training in banks operating in Jordan in reducing computer fraud.

5.2.2 The Result of the Second Hypothesis Test:

H₂: There is a positive relationship between awareness and training and adapting to cyber risks. This hypothesis has been subjected to (Simple Linear Regression) analysis, and the results shown in Table (4) have been reached.

Table 4: Results of the simple linear regression model for the second hypothesis

Model Summary			ANOVA			Coefficient					
R	R ²	Adj R ²	F	F.Sig	DF	Description	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig
0.719	0.517	0.515	246.297	0.00	231	Awareness and training	0.706	0.045	0.719	15.694	0.00

Table (4) indicates that the value of the correlation coefficient is (R=0.719), which indicates a strong relationship between awareness, training and adaptation to cyber risks. Also, the value of the correlation coefficient is (R=0.517), which indicates that (51.7%) of the variance was able to be explained by raising awareness and training in adapting to cyber risks.

We note from the results of the table that there is a statistically significant effect of awareness and training in adapting to cyber risks, which appears through the value of (T.Sig) and equal to

(0.00), which is less than (0.05) and also through the value of (T) calculated and equal to (15.694), which is greater than its tabulated value (1.96). Accordingly, we accept hypothesis H2, where it has been proven that there is a positive statistically significant effect of awareness and training in banks operating in Jordan and adapting to cyber risks.

5.2.3 The Result of the Third Hypothesis Test:

H3: There is a positive relationship between adapting to cyber risks and reducing computer fraud. This hypothesis was subjected to (Simple Linear Regression) analysis, and the results shown in Table (5) were reached.

Table 5: Results of the simple linear regression model for the third hypothesis

Model Summary			ANOVA			Coefficient					
R	R ²	Adj R ²	F	F.Sig	DF	statement	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig
0.817	0.668	0.666	462.367	0.00	231	Adapting to cyber risks	0.980	0.046	0.817	21.503	0.00

Table (5) indicates that the value of the correlation coefficient of (R = 0.817), which indicates that there is a strong relationship between adaptation to cyber risks and the reduction of computer fraud. Also, the value of (R = 0.668) which indicates that (66.8%) of the discrepancy may be explained by adapting to cyber risks in reducing computer fraud.

We note from the results of the table that there is a statistically significant effect of adapting to cyber risks in reducing computer fraud, which appears through the value of (T.Sig) and equal to (0.00), which is less than (0.05) and also through the value of (T) calculated and equal to (21.503), which is greater than its tabular value (1.96). Accordingly, we accept hypothesis H3, where it was proven that there is a positive and statistically significant effect of adapting to cyber risks in operating banks and reducing computer fraud.

5.2.4 The Result of the Fourth Hypothesis Test:

H4: Adapting to cyber risks mediates the relationship between awareness and training and reducing computer fraud. To analyze this hypothesis, path analysis was used using the Amos program supported by the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), and its results were as shown in Table (6) and Figure (1), where it was found that there is a statistically significant effect of awareness and training reducing computer fraud in the presence of adapting to cyber risks as a mediating variable, which appears through the result of the chi-square test (43.852 = Chi2), which is greater than the tabular value (30.14), as well as through the test (2.308CMIN/DF =), which is statistically significant amounted to (P=0.013), which is less than (0.05) (Hair et.al. 2018: 577-580).

The results also showed that the quality-fitness index (GFI = 0.979), which is close to a true one, as the closer it is to a true one, indicates the good-enough fit of the quality in the model (Good-Enough Fit). The comparative fit index (CFI = 0.981) is also close to a true one, in addition to that, the root mean square error-index is (RMSEA = 0.071), which is close to zero, which supports the good fit of the model (Byrne, 2010: 77). It was found that the direct

normative effect of awareness and training towards adaptation to cyber risks was (0.744) with a level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), while the direct normative effect of adaptation with cyber risks towards reducing computer fraud was (0.844), and the direct normative effect of awareness and training reached towards the reduction of computer fraud (0.034). The indirect normative effect of awareness and training in reducing computer fraud by having adaptation to cyber risks as a mediating variable was (0.627). Accordingly, awareness and training were able to explain (62.7%) as an indirect effect in reducing computer fraud, with adaptation to cyber risks as a mediating variable. Based on the foregoing, we accept hypothesis H4, which indicates that adapting to cyber risks mediates the relationship between awareness and training and reducing computer fraud.

Table 6: Path analysis test results for the fourth hypothesis

dependent	Chi ²	Tabulated Chi ²	CMIN/DF	GFI	CFI	RMSEA	P	Variables	Effect	Indirect effect	Total effect
Computer fraud	43.852	30.14	2.308	0.979	0.981	0.071	0.013	Awareness and Training Adaptation to Cyber Risks	0.744	---	0.744
								Adapting to Cyber Risks → Reducing Computer Fraud	0.844	---	0.844
								Awareness and Training → Adapting to Cyber Risks → Reducing Computer Fraud	0.034	0.627	0.661

Fig. 2: Path analysis test results to verify the direct and indirect effect of awareness and training in reducing computer fraud with cyber risk adaptation as a mediating variable

6. Conclusion

Organizations are increasingly concerned about fraud and threats to data confidentiality, integrity and availability, cyber risks and fraud are rapidly evolving. Thus, more work is needed in this area and collaboration between governments, academia, and industry. In this manner, this study has focused on investigate the mediating effect of adapting cyber risks on the relationship between awareness, training and reducing computer fraud in Jordanian banking sector.

The results of the study determined that there is a significant effect of awareness and training in reducing computer fraud. For mediating, the significant mediating of adapting cybersecurity risks was found among the relationship of awareness and training, and reducing computer fraud. Therefore, it is very necessary to increase awareness and training for the employees of the banking sector in particular by having the appropriate software skills to avoid falling into the trap of cyber security violations that incur their institutions. Also, there is a need to keep abreast of the issue of continuous updating of these software in order to keep pace with the rapid development in fraud methods that arise as the banking system developing. Banking system environment members should take in their accounts that they should pay their attentions to provide themselves by the skills, software, protection systems and any other necessary instruments to avoid or mitigate threats of cyber-security breakthroughs.

Like all research, this study has some limitations that could be addressed in future research. First, data was collected from banking sector located in Jordan; for wider focus, future studies may include a larger number of organizations to include wider population. Secondly, our research was focused on Jordan, which is a developing economy, so more studies are suggested focusing on other developing economies to understand wider economic and cultural implications. Thirdly, future studies can examine and revise this study's proposed model in order to increase its accurateness and aptness in other contexts. Also, it can allow different situations, business sectors, and even nations to be compared with the use of the revised model. Finally, the use of quantitative data makes this study limited. Hence, future studies could employ several stages of interviews to provide better depiction of factors reducing computer fraud.

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